

Supplementary Material for *Morphological Leave-One-Out Kernel Density Estimates for Anomaly Detection in Satellite Telemetry*

Mina Bikhit¹, Sevvandi Kandanaarachchi², Krzysztof Kotowski⁴,
Jakub Nalepa^{3,4}, and Bogdan Ruszczak¹

¹ Faculty of Computer Science, Opole University of Technology, Opole, Poland
`mina.bikhit@student.po.edu.pl`, `b.ruszczak@po.edu.pl`

² Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), Clayton,
VIC, Australia `Sevvandi.Kandanaarachchi@data61.csiro.au`

³ KP Labs, Gliwice, Poland `{kkotowski,jnalepa}@kplabs.pl`

⁴ Faculty of Automatic Control, Electronics and Computer Science, Silesian
University of Technology, Gliwice, Poland `jnalepa@ieee.org`

Abstract. This is the supplementary material for the main paper: Morphological Leave-One-Out Kernel Density Estimates for Anomaly Detection in Satellite Telemetry. We provide several additional tables, figures, and a detailed algorithm within this document.

Keywords: Anomaly detection · Leave-one-out kernel density estimates · Extreme Value Theory · Kernel density estimates · Generalized Pareto distribution · Satellite telemetry · ESA-ADB · Artificial intelligence.

1 Additional Details on the Employed Detector

For the calculation of the anomaly scores, we utilize the adopted LOO-KDE (Leave-One-Out Kernel Density Estimates [4]) Algorithm 1. After the initial ablation study for the utilized anomaly detector, we employed LOO-KDE with $\alpha = 0.05$ and bandwidth = 0.97, and in the later stage of the described experiments, we updated α and bandwidth to the values that rendered the best experimental results.

2 Additional Benchmarking Results

The detailed results for the evaluated approach, in terms of the algorithm memory consumption and the inference time, are summarized in Table 1. We provide separate results for all tested datasets and for each of the telemetry channels, as well as aggregated and averaged figures.

The reference results from deep learning-based, unsupervised, and semi-supervised models are gathered in Table 2. We computed the figures for Telemanom-ESA [2,6], Anomaly Transformer [8], and AnomalyBERT [3] for a comparison with the Mo-LOO-KDE algorithm presented in the main paper. Additionally,

Algorithm 1: *The adaptation of the LOO-KDE algorithm [4].*

- Input** : The data matrix \mathbf{X} , parameters α and *unitize*.
Output : The outliers, the GPD probabilities of all points, GPD parameters and bandwidth
- 1 If *unitize* = *TRUE*, then normalize the data so that each column is scaled to $[0, 1]$.
 - 2 Construct the persistence homology barcode of the data.
 - 3 Find d_* as the maximum death radius difference from the persistence homology barcode.
 - 4 Using $h = (d_*)^{2/p}$ and $\mathbf{H} = h\mathbf{I}$ compute KDE (kernel density estimates) and LOO-KDE (leave-one-out KDE) using the scaled Epanechnikov kernel.
 - 5 Denote the KDE of \mathbf{x}_i by y_i and LOO-KDE by y_{-i} .
 - 6 Using the POT approach fit a GPD to $\{-\log(y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ and find μ, σ and ξ . Using the GPD parameters μ, σ and ξ find the probability of the LOO-KDE values $\{-\log(y_{-i})\}_{i=1}^N$, i.e., $P(-\log(y_{-i})|\mu, \sigma, \xi)$ for all i .
 - 7 If $P(-\log(y_{-i})|\mu, \sigma, \xi) < \alpha$, then declare \mathbf{x}_i as an outlier.
-

Table 1: Mo-LOO-KDE performance on AMD Ryzen 9 7950X processor

Dataset length	Channel ID	Peak memory consumption [MB]	Inference time [s]
42 months	channel_41	2985.29	463.01
42 months	channel_42	3484.77	465.15
42 months	channel_43	4075.43	421.17
42 months	channel_44	4198.25	438.07
42 months	channel_45	4131.46	430.75
42 months	channel_46	3851.29	453.25
42 months	average	3787.74	445.23
10 months	channel_41	3630.95	99.87
10 months	channel_42	4200.84	104.87
10 months	channel_43	4004.00	100.29
10 months	channel_44	4618.32	99.22
10 months	channel_45	4355.27	102.89
10 months	channel_46	4873.02	103.54
10 months	average	4280.40	101.70

similarly to Mo-LOO-KDE, for the presented models, we report the results in two variants: computed for the “vanilla” model, and followed by postprocessing (indicated as ‘Mo-’ for morphological filtering described in the paper). It is worth noticing that the proposed postprocessing leads to significant improvements, also for the AnomalyBERT detector, allowing to raise event-wise precision from 0.785 to 0.985.

Table 2: The reference results from deep learning models for Telemanom and transformer-based models (upper part of the table) and detections with an additional morphological filtering step (lower part of the table). The best results for each metric are boldfaced.

Evaluated algorithm	Point- Pr_p	Event- wise metrics			Number of detections		
		Pr_e	Re_e	$F_{0.5e}$	TP_e	FP_e	FN_e
Telemanom-ESA ^b [2,6]	–	0.148	0.894	0.178	–	–	–
Telemanom-ESA-Pruned ^b [2,6]	–	0.999	0.424	0.786	–	–	–
Anomaly Transformer [8]	0.0005	0.300	1.000	0.348	3	7	0
AnomalyBERT [3]	0.015	0.785	1.000	0.820	66	18	0
Mo-Anomaly Transformer	0.0005	0.272	1.000	0.319	3	8	0
Mo-AnomalyBERT	0.015	0.985	1.000	0.988	66	1	0

^aCalculated using [6].

^bResults reported in: ESA Benchmark for Anomaly Detection in satellite telemetry [5].

The comparison of the event-wise metrics for the evaluated models should be done without any knowledge of the general differences between these algorithms. Mo-LOO-KDE is an unsupervised architecture and does not require any initial training phase, which is fundamentally different from other (supervised) models.

We compared the model performance in terms of the main memory consumption as well as the training and inference time, and the consumption of the accelerator memory for those models that operate on a GPU. Table 3 provides the detailed figures for the investigated models. We employed the Ryzen 9 7950X CPU and the NVIDIA 5080 GPU. The metrics for Mo-LOO-KDE are averaged across channels. For the Anomaly Transformer, we utilized a pretrained model. We performed those tests using a longer, 42-month-long training dataset, whereas for the AnomalyBERT, we trained the model from scratch, and the time spent on this process is also summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of the model performance, memory usage, and GPU utilization for the investigated models.

	AnomalyBERT	Anomaly Transformer	Mo LOO KDE
Training Time (42M)	1h 10m 34s	1m 2s	–
Inference Time (42M)	5m 33s	37s	7m 33s
RAM	3.46 GB	2.20 GB	3.60 GB
GPU RAM	1.32 GB	3.37 GB	–
GPU Utilization	99.00%	88.00%	–

3 Visualizing the Filtering Performance

The figures provided below present a supplementary view of the investigated detections. In Figure 1, we depict a closer look at a fragment of the telemetry

timeseries and a part of the generated predictions. We showcase the differences between the predictions of each evaluated model. Additionally, the effect of morphological filtering of the detections is emphasized. One could notice a significant reduction in the false positives for the applied postprocessing.

Acknowledgments. This work was financially supported by the Opole University of Technology as part of the DELTA project no. 272/24.

References

1. Aggarwal, C.C.: Linear Models for Outlier Detection, pp. 65–110. Springer International Publishing (2017). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-47578-3_3
2. Hundman, K., Constantinou, V., et al.: Detecting spacecraft anomalies using lstms and nonparametric dynamic thresholding. p. 387–395. KDD '18, ACM (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3219819.3219845>
3. Jeong, Y., Yang, E., Ryu, J.H., Park, I., Kang, M.: AnomalyBERT: Self-supervised transformer for time series anomaly detection using data degradation scheme. arXiv preprint [arXiv:2305.04468](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.04468) (2023), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.04468>, code: <https://github.com/Jhryu30/AnomalyBERT>
4. Kandanaarachchi, S., Hyndman, R.J.: Leave-One-Out Kernel Density Estimates for outlier detection. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics* **31**(2), 586–599 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10618600.2021.2000425>
5. Kotowski, K., et al.: European Space Agency Benchmark for Anomaly Detection in satellite telemetry (2024), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.17826>
6. KP Labs: Code of the ESA Anomaly Detection Benchmark, github.com/kplabs-pl/ESA-ADB
7. Ruff, L., Vandermeulen, R., et al.: Deep One-Class Classification. In: 35th ICML. vol. 80 (2018), <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v80/ruff18a.html>
8. Xu, J., Wu, H., et al.: Anomaly Transformer: Time Series Anomaly Detection with Association Discrepancy. In: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR) Spotlight (2022), https://openreview.net/forum?id=LzQQ89U1qm_

Fig. 1: The output of 6 models tested on *ESA-ADB, Mission #1, Channel_45* with a closer look at six days of the series only. A comparison of the original model with its *Mo*- variant is shown. Row 1: LOO-KDE [4], Row 2: Mo-LOO-KDE, Row 3: Autoencoder [1], Row 4: Mo-Autoencoder, Row 5: DeepSVDD (Deep Support Vector Data Description [7]), Row 6: Mo-DeepSVDD.